

The Precursor Models in Natural Sciences Learning and Teaching

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Abstract. The current study deals with the theoretical framework within which the concept of the precursor model in learning and teaching science emerges. By traversing two complementary paths, from observation of the natural world to mental representations and from scientific theories to school scientific models, the concept of the precursor model through the identification of its key features is scrutiny presented. In addition, drawing from two distinct research studies of precursor models on the concept of force in secondary education and the concept of friction in preschool education, important questions about the nature and character of precursor models are analyzed and discussed.

1 Introduction

The constitution of Science Education as an autonomous scientific area with strong productive processes at the level of theory, methodology and application, was founded on: (a) the socially established need for the creation of better trained scientific and technological personnel in various countries of the world in very different phases of their economic development, (b) the maturation of scientific areas such as Genetic Epistemology, Cognitive, Developmental and Educational Psychology and (c) the ineffective reforms within the framework of traditional study streams of teaching Physics, Chemistry, Biology etc. The above-mentioned dimensions led to the search for the role and impact of children's everyday experiences on the way they approach the natural world and conceptualize Natural Sciences.

The second dimension, namely the recognition in Psychology of the importance of students' spontaneous, experiential, naïve representations of the phenomena and concepts studied in the Natural Sciences, has created a huge stream of research. Despite the fact that these investigations hold their origins from different theoretical backgrounds, they continue to reveal the patterns of thinking and reasoning of children at different stages of their development and schooling. These representations of children are well known in the international literature as misconceptions, ideas, alternative conceptions, perceptions etc [1-5]. While it is, perhaps, a paradox that the international community has not managed to consolidate a uniform terminology so far, it seems that this is a systematic pathology of the social sciences field and therefore will not concern us here. Hence, we will adopt the term 'mental representation' which is considered more appropriate, since it encapsulates extensive discussions of different areas of research on the fundamental question of learning, such as

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the structural and functional interactions with other entities of thought, an explanatory power, the cognitive dynamics they create etc [6,7].

When trying to move from the world of children's thinking to the issues of learning and teaching Natural Sciences, the recording of mental representations and the identification of the difficulties they create, allows to illuminate the distance between scientific school knowledge and students' reasoning. This makes it possible to develop teaching strategies whose one of the main objectives is to overcome children's obstacles due to mental representations and thus to transform them. Well known such strategies are inquiry-based learning approaches, 5E or 7E learning cycles, Search, Solve, Create, and Share method and Predict-Observe-Explain (POE) procedures [8-12]. Nevertheless, the question that arises here is whether the approach of Natural Sciences constitutes a simple issue of just reorganizing or transforming children's mental representations? As the structural elements of the Natural Sciences have a very different constitution from personal constructs of thought, we know that a real discussion about their systematic approach is directly related to theories, models, principles, laws, concepts, etc.

Consequently, the issue of effective teaching and learning of Natural Sciences hold three basic dimensions:

(a) the first one, is related to students' thinking, i.e. the possibilities, difficulties and obstacles they face,

(b) the second dimension relates to the entities drawn from Natural Sciences as they are transformed in order to be suitable for the different levels of education

(c) the third dimension deals with the design and implementation of teaching procedures that allow students with different characteristics to approach knowledge from Natural Sciences as it is shaped for school content.

In what follows, we will try to deal with the construction of models from Natural Sciences within the education field. Along this line we will mainly highlight the dimensions of a particular theoretical construction, that of 'precursor models'. However, it should be made clear that the approach we adopt here is closely tied to the concept of 'learning', leaving aside fundamental issues such as the cultural environment, the curriculum, the development of general mental skills or values etc.

2 Towards the concept of Natural Science models for education

The term 'model' is used in a simplistic way in everyday life, as well as in diverse sciences, denoting a series of entities with distinct qualitative characteristics. For example, in Cognitive Science, models are imperfect mental entities due to constraints caused by perceptual and cognitive factors, they have internal structure and possibilities of creating relations among them [13,14], while in the Educational Sciences models are structures that define and describe interactions at the level of the educational system, the school unit or teaching and pedagogical relations [15,16]. In the Natural Sciences, in the context of epistemological ambiguity, quite often principles, theories and laws are identified as models, while in many cases the term is used to convey mathematical expressions of a regularity, three-dimensional constructions, virtual or schematic representations of states, experimental arrangements, etc.

This polysemy, which is encountered within various science fields as well, was transferred to Science Education and actually enlarged as in the field of study of Science Education the Natural Sciences on the one hand by and the Social Sciences on the other converge. In addition, as Science Education became autonomous as a science, the concepts used within it were reconstructed and acquired relative conceptual autonomy. Unfortunately, the inherited confusion about the concept of the model was not only transferred to Science Education, but also began to acquire new features. Thus, for example, naïve mental representations or scientific constructs of any kind that are transferred into teaching directly

from reference sciences, such as Physics or Chemistry, are often characterized as models. So, by just talking about ‘model’ or better ‘school scientific model’ we are not at all sure that we all mean the same entity. Hence, our goal is to try, in an inevitably schematic way, to define the meaning and identity of the concept of model within Science Education field.

Firstly, the issue of the human thought approach to Natural Science in education has two simultaneous ‘entrances’. The first relates to science itself as it is constituted and shaped for education, while the second to the natural world in which people have their first experiences which are extremely important.

At the level of science, the formulation of integrated approaches leads to the creation of theories, which are large-scale constructions that attempt to depict in an abstract and symbolic way structural and functional relationships of physical reality (Figure 1a). A theory that is created and matures over time, approaches and interprets a wide range of phenomena that are amenable to common patterns of interpretation and are studied with given methodological tools. Typical examples of theories are Relativity in Physics or Evolution in Biology.

Fig. 1. The precursor models between School Scientific Model and Mental Representations.

The nature and range of theories impose specialized approaches that serve ‘local’ solutions in understanding and schematizing specific phenomena. It is precisely these approaches that are identified as scientific models (Figure 1b). “The heart of a scientific theory is not constituted by a set of axioms and laws, but by a set of models” [17, p. 45]. Models include as their structural elements “hypothetical entities and a set of interconnected concepts that serve to describe these entities” [18, p. 57].

These models actually act as the origins of school scientific models which are fundamental elements of school knowledge (Figure 1c). Indeed, school knowledge along the path from preschool to secondary education develops at higher levels of abstraction and gradually expands in terms of subject matter, remaining concentrated around basic models

of the Natural Sciences [19,20]. These models, such as for example Geometrical Optics or Bohr's atomic structure of matter, are basic entities for the foundation of Natural Sciences and in order to be integrated into education they undergo processes of transformation and adaptation which are studied in the theories of 'Pedagogical Content Knowledge' [21] and 'Didactic Transposition' [22,23] or approaches that invoke the 'simplification' of scientific knowledge [24].

On the contrary, the constant immersion of human beings and social-collective entities in the physical world creates a powerful and continuous source of stimuli that impose on thought an undifferentiated series of experiences, images and associations (Figure 1d). The perceptual pathway of cognition is thus in constant stimulation and the addition and alternation of experiences raise questions and probe for possible answers. However, everyday contact with the natural world does not offer any criteria that allow for an organized and systematic investigation and schematization.

Of course, everyday life is a constant source of specific challenges in many dimensions covering a wide range that start from powerful phenomena of the wider human environment such as earthquakes, weather and climate, volcanoes, fires, floods, etc. and extend to phenomena recognized during the use of conventional or digital technology at home, work, health, etc (Figure 1e). Gradually, human thought at the individual, collective or social level focuses on specific phenomena whose reception is in constant interaction with the public understanding of scientific knowledge as reflected in the mechanisms of popularization of knowledge such as the media, social media etc. The study of some of these phenomena is also chosen as a subject of work in school curricula, after they have been allocated to different school and age levels on the basis of certain explicit or implicit criteria. During the study of the phenomena, an attempt is made to bring the students' thinking closer to scientific school knowledge. The basic premise of this approach attempt is the identification of the critical difficulties faced by the student's thinking [25-28].

Thus, along the path from the reception of stimuli from the natural world to the approach of Natural Sciences, we inevitably pass through the mental representations we referred to in the introduction (Figure 1f). The distance of these entities of thought from scientific school knowledge underlines an important dimension of the effort to be made and that is why the possibilities of specially designed teaching interventions at the level of the individual, the group or the actual classroom are constantly being tested. Many years of research have shown that mental representations of concepts or phenomena of the Natural Sciences have certain characteristics: they are naïve, implicit, local, non-conscious [29,30]. That is why their transformation, although it seems to lead to new reasoning, often weakens over time, is easily destabilized in the face of new empirical data and merges without rules with conventional school knowledge giving hybrid mental entities.

However, a crucial question is the orientation of these efforts. What exactly is the knowledge to which we want to lead students' thinking? What is the direction of the desired changes in mental representations? Quite often this question is avoided or has no clear answer. In a realistic direction, our interest confine in the knowledge included in school programs or textbooks, as well as to just some changes in understanding and interpretations of natural phenomena or encompass the development of skills that allow improvement in problem solving.

Without underestimating any of the above mentioned points, a wide range of research streams often lead to a fundamental finding: school scientific knowledge is not constituted as a series of independently satisfactory mental representations or effective problem-solving skills, but as models whose structure and scope have some particular characteristics [31]. These models, as described earlier, are transformed versions of scientific models through specialized processes.

We mentioned earlier the two ‘entrances’ of the approach to human thought in Natural Sciences. When these entrances lead to the field of education we saw that: (a) From the point of view of natural-experiential reasoning and human everyday experience we end up with the strong presence of mental representations in children's thinking and (b) From the side of science itself we meet, through a path of adaptations of scientific knowledge, the models that are created for the purpose of learning and teaching Natural Sciences.

The recognition of the importance of these two dimensions, in a rational perspective that is not always self-evident, raises in a clear way the question of the transition from mental representations to the mental constitution of models. The issue, although not exhaustive, is familiar in the literature in approaches characterized by the term ‘modeling’. It is a fact that a range of different perspectives are recorded in the literature as epistemological, psychological, cognitive and didactic parameters create and often multiply complexity [32]. These concerns are open and, despite their scope, or rather because of their scope, highlight the need for more specific approaches. For example, the question of the ‘transition from mental representations to models’ that we have posed is doubtful whether it can be answered in a general way. Along this process, let's assume that we set aside fundamental issues such as programs, objectives, textbooks, school laboratory work, different strategies of teaching interventions, etc. Keeping only two basic factors in mind, namely: (a) the variety of curricular subjects that come from distinct bodies of knowledge such as Physics, Chemistry or Biology and (b) the age range of students that extends from early childhood education to university, it is obvious that it is difficult to determine the necessary advances in students' thinking in order to claim that the transition from mental representations to scientific school models has taken place.

We are also well aware that the mental construction of a model is a long-term process that takes place gradually and assumes that students are actively involved in specially designed teaching interventions. Therefore, when we talk about ‘transition’ we mean more of a pathway and less of a final state.

This is why it is particularly important to study the way students think along this process. This finding, however, must not be of a general character referring to certain observed improvements or changes, but to those which contribute to the gradual formation of models in children's thinking.

3 The Precursor Models

Along this perspective the concept of the ‘precursor model’ was proposed [18,33,34] which in the context of the relevant research was developed and gave interesting results [35-37]. “The term ‘precursor’ together with the word ‘model’ means it is a case of models that prepare for the elaboration of other models. Consequently, precursor models consist of a certain number of elements characteristic of the scholarly models towards which they strive. These elements may concern hypothetical entities and thinking operations associated with the handling of these entities or symbolic representations. Precursor models necessarily have a reduced field of validity compared with scholarly models..... thus constitute didactic constructions designed to help pupils access scholarly models. They are therefore precursors in regard to cognitive development” [18, p. 26].

Therefore, if precursor models are elements compatible with certain features of school scientific models, it seems that they could be the appropriate entities to be grasped by students and interposed between school scientific models and mental representations. In the concept of precursor model, at the level of learning, we find established cognitive difficulties of children and elements of school models that we want students to understand [38-40]. Thus, at the level of teaching, we offer the ‘starting points’ and ‘arrival points’ of the path that teachers and students have to follow in order to form in children's minds stable entities which

have contents, structural and/or functional elements compatible with those of school models and therefore create solid conditions to prepare students for the formation of real school scientific models.

An important element of this process is the identification of the structural and functional elements of the school models which have specificities and differences due to the various teaching subjects and distinct characteristics which are found in each model. However, it should be clear that this discussion is exclusively concerned with school scientific models and therefore we limit ourselves to models that have three basic characteristics:

- originate from Natural Sciences field,
- formatted for the needs of education and
- become the object of instruction and mental processing in the context of didactic circumstances.

3.1 Structure, content and functions of models and precursor models

In a rational approach within the context of Science Education, school scientific models are constructed by a structured process of transformation of scientific models. These models inevitably have distinct characteristics due to the different objects of study and the ages of the children they concern. Indeed, undisputably the fundamental characteristics of a model for understanding a simple electrical circuit and the eruption of a volcano are different. Similarly, a model for the dissolution of a solid into a liquid differs itself in case it is constructed for children in the early years of primary education or for pupils at the end of secondary education. Despite these differences, however, there are common elements which enable us to describe certain entities of thought as scientific models [41-44].

In terms of structure and content, the school scientific models have a number of elements that constitute the key features of their identity.

- **The concepts.** These are the basic elements of models as they determine the type of phenomena that can be approached.
- **The empirical and experimental field of reference.** This field consists of the delimited set of empirical situations in which the use of the model allows the interpretation of phenomena.
- **The syntactic relationships.** In addition to concepts, models also include other types of normative entities such as laws or principles. All these elements are connected in specific ways and these connections are captured by symbols and mathematical relations to make the model functional.
- **The semantic relations.** In order to maintain systematic communication between models and phenomena, there is a need for precise correspondences among the symbolic elements of the model and the empirical elements of the phenomenon considered by the model.

Regarding the functions of the school models that are intended to be constituted in students' thinking during the learning processes, three levels are distinguished:

- **The description.** The description of systems, their relationships and their changes in science teaching does not coincide with simple observation. It requires the use of criteria which the structure and content of models are able to provide.
- **The explanation.** The exploitation of data and the relationships among the elements of a model allows the creation of causal correlations and thus interprets the observed processes and the generated results.
- **The prediction.** The models enable the thought to select and combine its elements so that it can be successfully extended to new but related topics and fields of application. It is a creative possibility to address new problems and phenomena by formulating hypotheses, creating correlations and abstractly reconstructing the observed events.

The constitution of a model in students' mind presupposes the ability to handle the necessary structural and functional elements of the models, as they are depicted in the preceding schematic presentation. The differences in the levels of abstraction and the number of the structural and functional characteristics of the models make it clear that the teaching processes which aim at their formation in students' minds are complex and require an instructional design with a wide range in time and specific provisions in the curricula. Therefore, in a learning and developmental perspective, great importance is attached to the course itself during which individual possibilities of thinking are developed. Thus, we could work on the formation in the thinking of pupils of all ages of distinct elements such as, for example, concepts at the level of structure and content or predictions at the functional level.

This is exactly the role of precursor models since they integrate these capabilities in the framework of entities compatible with the school scientific models while structured in such a way that hold a stable content and function.

3.2 The precursor models in the research framework

In the process of models' construction, the importance and role of precursor models is highlighted. Indeed, as time and successive teaching processes are required, the construction of stable entities with characteristics compatible with those of school scientific models in students' minds, can play a decisive role in a gradual developmental path leading to the mastery of the models.

In what follows we present two typical examples of precursor models that research has shown they worked successfully in the thinking of students from two completely different age groups. In particular, the first refers to the construction of a precursor model for the concept of force with secondary school students while the second to the processing of a precursor model for friction with preschoolers.

3.2.1 Interaction as a precursor model of force for secondary school students

In the context of school Newtonian mechanics, force is a vectorial quantity that describes contact or remote interactions. This entity is a symmetrical relationship between systems, which distinguishes it from other physical quantities taught which describe the characteristics of objects or systems. Force, with its scalar, algebraic and vectorial forms and its relation to motion and concepts such as velocity and acceleration, is known for its difficulty, which has already been well documented by research in Science Education [45-47]. The difficulty is multiplied by several other factors such as, for example, the use of language where force is encountered as a property of bodies and living organisms, or the fact that interacting bodies are presented in the form of everyday objects whereas in the model are counted as material points.

Therefore, in order to study the concept of force and address its complexity, an attempt was made in a study with students at the end of secondary schooling to formulate in their minds a precursor model focused on the concept of 'interaction' which is a constant cognitive barrier. This choice aims to help students to conceptualize the mutual actions of interacting systems in advance of studying the effects of exerting forces on bodies-material points. The advantage of such a precursor model is that it is defined by a limited set of assumptions which can be applied incrementally to easily controlled conditions, such as immobility or the induction of motion [18,33,34].

Researchers start the study of the interaction issue using body X which is related to bodies A and B. The three assumptions on the basis of which students explore a series of situations involving immobility or displacement in one direction are the following:

“(a) The ‘act on’ hypothesis. An object acts or does not act on another object. The verb ‘act’ is used instead of a whole series of verbs that students spontaneously suggest such as ‘push’, ‘draw’, ‘retain’, ‘support’, etc. These verbs express modes of relationships between objects which are highly constrained by their intrinsic properties. (For example, a big slab of iron ‘holds’ a spring, the table ‘supports’ a book, etc.) ‘Act’ expresses the feature common to a relationship between objects, the fact of existing or not, regardless of the objects in question.

(b) The reciprocity hypothesis. If an object A acts on an object B, then object B acts on object A, regardless of the nature of objects A and B. Objects A and B interact or do not interact.

(c) The hypothesis of the ‘strength’ of the relationship between act and events. Two types of events were approached: immobility and changes in motion:

- immobility: object X is immobile, if under the influence of two objects A and B, these objects act on X equally.
- change in motion: object X changes motion if it is influenced by another object or if, when under the influence of objects A and B, one acts on X more than the other” [48, pp. 25-26].

Fig. 2. The interaction model.

Horizontal spring : compare the length
 Spring stretched by two similar objects

object A and an object heavier than A on a table

object A and one hand

Vertical spring stretched by an object A

- fastened to a cross-piece
- held in a hand.

Reading a scale:

- a ball denser than water is on the pan of a scale,
- in the jar of water,
- hung on a string.

two magnets one above the other,

- attract each other,
- repel each other,
- one is hung.

“a person with a stick,

- is pushing on the ground,
- is pushing on the scale,
- is pushing on the ceiling.

Fig. 3. The experimental situations.

Based on these assumptions, a series of experimental situations was followed (Figure 3), which were systematically exploited during the collaboration between researchers and students in order to gradually construct the precursor model of the interactions.

Systematic work with these experimental situations led to two main findings:

(a) This precursor model allowed the creation of new cognitive processes in students' thinking, such as grouping objects in a system, the ability to use a principle in consistency as well as the acquisition of mental processes of induction and deduction.

(b) Based on this precursor model of interaction, the researchers showed that it is possible to understand the concept of force defined in terms of its set of characteristics and its functions as provided in the school model, using of course more complex experimental situations.

3.2.2 A precursor model of friction in the thinking of preschool children

According to 'laws of friction', when two bodies touch and slide against each other, each of them is subjected to a force called 'sliding friction'. The frictional force depends on several factors such as the degree of grinding of the materials of which the bodies are composed, the presence or absence of air or other fluid between the surfaces, the elastic or plastic nature of the materials, the speed of the moving bodies etc.

However, the school model, neglecting the other variables, relates the development of the sliding friction force to two factors: (a) the vertical force between bodies that are touching and moving relative to each other and (b) the nature of the touching surfaces. In its simplest form, the problem of the occurrence of friction is limited to the movement of an object on a constant horizontal plane, under the influence of a horizontal force. In this movement the applied vertical force from the plane to the body is equal to the weight of the object, and therefore we can consider as a factor the weight of the moving body itself [49,59].

In early childhood programs, the issue of discovering the physical properties and behaviors of bodies in interaction is important. In this context, friction is an interesting topic which is approached in activities carried out in an implicit or explicit way. The attempt to bring preschool children into contact with the force of sliding friction encounters insurmountable obstacles from the outset: force as a concept has considerable difficulties which we have already touched on and even if we could rely on some intuitive approach to it, friction is a force whose conditions of generation or causes of occurrence are not understood. Consequently, for children of early childhood, the didactic approach to friction cannot be made through the factors on which the force of friction depends. We therefore tried to guide children in constructing a precursor model of friction, with its main elements being the factors that prevent the movement of a body on a horizontal floor, that is to understand the role of (a) the nature of the floor and moving body surfaces and (b) the weight of the body [51].

In this perspective, a playful teaching process was designed and implemented. With a specially constructed device ('the projecting apparatus') with which small boxes moving along a treadmill (Figure 4) were ejected in a stable manner, the following were used: (a) boxes to which we were able to add or remove objects with different weights measured on a 'lighter-heavier' quality scale and (b) tangential box and floor surfaces whose nature was also assessed on a qualitative scale 'smoother-rougher', using aisles of smooth plastic material or carpets and other materials for the outer surface of the box. With successive tests in which only one variable varied at a time (the weight of the moving body, the nature of the floor of the device or the nature of the body surfaces), we were led to the mental processing and construction of a precursor model for sliding friction. This model allowed children to describe and predict the effects on body movement due to the change in the two factors on which friction depends, without mentioning at all the concept of sliding friction force.

Fig. 4. The projecting apparatus.

These teaching activities on sliding friction were later extended to other research on rolling friction, also based on similar playful processes [52]. Thus, we found that children can gradually construct with stability in their thinking the conditions under which the movement of one body over another is facilitated or hindered. Being able to recognize from 5-6 years old the factors that are counted in education context as the basics to understand the concept of friction without any reference to it, gives children the capability to constitute a precursor model for friction. On this model may children later refer in order to construct a real understanding of the structural and functional characteristics of the concept.

4 Discussion

In the current paper we tried to approach the nature of precursor models and their potential role in science learning and teaching. As we have seen, since they are placed between school scientific models and students' mental representations of the concepts and phenomena considered in science, precursor models seem to take on a completely different form for each particular subject. Thus, while they are constituted with some of the structural and functional elements of the models, due to the diversity and instability of mental representations and the need to organize different types of heuristic teaching interventions with very specific goals, precursor models are not characterized by homogeneity [53,54].

Another important element is the need to adapt precursor models to the age of students they are intended to address, with a double scope: (a) on the one hand, to respond to the potential of children as they have developed, in the different contexts in which they operate both in their daily lives and school, and (b) on the other hand, to support a developmental perspective of children's thinking, i.e. lead to a functional tool for approaching natural phenomena, a tool that is compatible with the school scientific model.

The questions raised by such a research perspective are several [55,56]. We will just mention two of them to underline the profound difficulties: (a) The first question relates to the number of precursor models necessary to lead to the constitution of the school model, their arrangement and succession in time, and the processes of cooperation among them in students' thinking. (b) The second question relates to the gradual broadening of their fields of application, i.e. the phenomena which they are able to approach. Considering the wide range of models that we are working on, in learning and teaching Natural Sciences at all levels of education, a research program based on the expectation of creating precursor models seems unrealistic. However, constructing precursor models in selected learning areas could offer satisfactory solutions.

In closing this discussion, an important question that often arises in every acquisition of children's thinking in a constructivist framework is the following: what is the criterion of successful learning? Certainly not giving a 'correct' answer after teaching nor an answer that

is improved over what a naïve mental representation allows. The central issue at the level of learning outcomes is the stability of new cognitive tools over time. Indeed, in the dominant theoretical framework within which we work in Science Education, it is a fundamental matter to construct knowledge, that is to create new entities of thought that when constructed remain stable. Much more so, this requirement is strong when we invoke the creation of any type of models whose basic characteristics are structure, content and functions. This is precisely the requirement we have from precursor models, and despite their limited scope, stability seems the most important criterion for constructing them. This perspective is an important research dimension that is gradually developing.

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